

**ОЦІНКА СТРАТЕГІЇ
СТАЛОГО РОЗВИТКУ
СИСТЕМИ ОХОРОНИ ЗДОРОВ'Я УКРАЇНИ
В УМОВАХ ВІЙНИ**

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До розділу: організація охорони здоров'я.

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У роботі розглянуті питання публічного управління медичною системою України на прикладі Харківського регіону. Проведено порівняння системи управління з існуючими моделями управління, які визнані ВООЗ «кращими практиками».

Ключові слова: управління охороною здоров'я, реформа охорони здоров'я, сталий розвиток.

**ASSESSMENT OF THE SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY
FOR THE HEALTH CARE SYSTEM OF UKRAINE
IN THE CONDITIONS OF WAR**

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The work examines issues of public management of the medical system of Ukraine using the example of the Kharkiv region. A comparison of the management system with existing management models, which are recognized by the WHO as "best practices", was executed.

Keywords: health care management, health care reform, sustainable development.

Comparing the experience of the organization and public management of the medical system of Ukraine and the Kharkiv region with other countries, the importance of state care over the health care system of developed countries is noticeable and obvious, especially through the lens of understanding the shortcomings in the market of medical services and concepts of social justice. Every person in the modern world has the right to receive a minimum level of medical care, regardless of their financial status, and it is the responsibility of the state to ensure this right. In most countries with a developed market economy, public health care systems have been created that are accessible to most citizens. In such countries, medical care is provided by both public and private medical institutions and doctors. Outpatient care is provided by general practitioners

and specialists of a narrow profile who work as individual entrepreneurs or in medical associations. Organizations similar to ordinary polyclinics are not common in all countries with developed market economies [1; 2].

Inpatient treatment is provided in public and private hospitals, which may include both non-commercial and commercial ones. The percentage of public and private medical organizations varies from country to country. Financing of medical care can be carried out at the expense of budget funds, which are formed from joint taxation, or at the expense of mandatory health insurance funds, which are formed from insurance contributions of employers and the state or pension and other social funds for the unemployed [3].

In countries with budget funding, each health provider was subordinated to an admi-

nistrative unit. In insurance financing systems, insurers usually do not have the right to choose the providers who would provide medical care to the insured. They were obliged to enter into agreements with any provider of medical services. Ukraine also strives for a similar model of medical care organization, and the Kharkiv region is taking the main steps recommended by the national reform strategy.

Formation of the main directions of state policy in the field of health care is carried out on the basis of Art. 3, 48, 49 of the Constitution of Ukraine. The need to reform the health care system in Ukraine and to find legal ways to overcome the problem of providing low-quality medical care prompts scientists, health care organizers, jurists and managers to conduct numerical studies [4]. The health care reform described above is carried out in accordance with the Program of Activities of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of the Sustainable Development Strategy "Ukraine-2020". In the latter, the goal of the state policy in the field of health care is spelled out and the main strategic goals of the reform are defined.

The Program of Activities of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine defines the following areas of activity:

- 1) elimination of corruption schemes during tender procurement in the health care system, transfer of the function of public procurement from the Ministry of Health, in particular to international organizations (2015-2016);
- 2) transformation and modernization of the network of hospitals and creation of a single three-level system (local hospitals – regional hospitals – national reference centers) (2017);
- 3) deregulation of the pharmaceutical market, a significant reduction in the number of licenses and permits (2015–2016).

From January 2022 until the start of a full-scale war, there was an active discussion of the Strategy for the Development of the Health Care System of Ukraine until 2030 [5] among legislators and scientists. The strategy was based on a patient-oriented principle, with emphasis on specialized narrow topics (oncological, orphan, and other diseases). Its implementation was expected to reduce patients' own medical expenses, increase the life expectancy of men to 70 years, women to 80 years (by 3 years), reduce maternal and child mortality to the average level of the European Union, reduce premature mortality from non-communicable diseases by a third, reducing the level of disability due to preventable diseases, reducing morbidity, disability and mortality from tuberculosis, HIV/AIDS, hepatitis C, traffic injuries, reducing salt consumption, etc.

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